

GREAT

GREAT TOOLKIT

How to utilise games to promote a positive impact on social engagement and create new forms of dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders.

Co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Programme – Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society: GREAT – Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation (societal and cultural domains), Grant agreement ID 101094766; and the UKRI, Grant agreement ID 10054160.

UK Research and Innovation

Co-funded by the European Union

Delivered By:

Project Context

Project Context & Overarching Methodology

The aim of GREAT is to harness digital games (short-scale mobile quizzes & deeper collaborative simulations) to engage citizens in climate-policy dialogue, blending quantitative (millions of players) and qualitative (small-group) data collection. The outcome being a more collaborative and inclusive approach to policy making.

Core methods:

- **Collaborative design** with citizens + policy stakeholders
- **Citizen-science** participatory gameplay within real-world contexts
- **Agile adaptation** of existing game platforms
- **Mixed-methods research** (mini-data sprints, surveys, interviews, simulations)

Read more here: [ECGBL Paper](#)

Why the GREAT Project?

- **Climate Change** is one of, if not **THE** challenge the global community faces
- Governments globally need to **engage with their citizens** if changes are to occur ... Evidence indicates (and voting habits) that many **younger citizens are disengaged** from the **political processes**...
- How do governments accurately gauge the **priorities of their citizens** if some are disengaged?
- **Technology** may offer (at least part) of the solution to this dilemma ... (engagement and Priorities)
- Digital Games **engage audiences** (globally) into the billions ...

Who is this Toolkit for?

The **GREAT Toolkit** and methodology can be used for a range of stakeholders who wish to leverage games technology to engage stakeholders and the wider public climate change actions including climate policy change. From small scale facilitated game play to large scale mass rollouts, the GREAT project has created the next level thinking, process and tools on how games can tackle global societal issues.

Games Studios

Better understand what their players care about and how to design their green content strategies to be more engaging and impactful.

Policy Makers

Co-ordinate a range of stakeholders to define a dilemma or policy challenge then engage the public at widescale.

Corporates

Better understand the questions they need to ask around a particular challenge then engage the wide-scale public for insights and action.

NB. Through the project process Playmob was acquired by PlanetPlay therefore any mention of Playmob is now as PlanetPlay.

How to Use This Toolkit

Overview Map: Match each WP → methodology → deliverables.

Model Extraction: Use for piloting design-driven game tools; blog papers and case reports for qualitative/quantitative research models.

Deployment Cycle: Follow the GREAT flow—design → pilot → analyze → refine guidance—for your own context including leveraging DiBL and PlanetPlay, together or individually.

Stakeholder Loop: Marvel at GREAT's “close-the-policy-loop”—ensuring real-world implications and feedback with authorities.

GREAT Project Video

GREAT

GAMES REALISING TRANSFORMATION

HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01-09 — Games and culture shaping our society

DESIGN CHALLENGES

Design, challenges, design briefs, and wireframes

Overview:

- Reports on work carried out in Intervention Design
- Summarizes 12 pilot activities conducted with users
- Provides basis for development of activity designs for GREAT case study protocol

GREAT D2.1 Summary report and compilation of design challenges, design...

D2.1 summarises the work carried out in WP 2 Intervention Design. A program of twelve pilots wa...

Zenodo

Figure 1: Steps 1,2 and 3 of the GREAT Case Study Cycle.

Design, challenges, design briefs, and wireframes

Key Findings:

- Pilots were effective in creating desired outcomes (design challenges, briefs, wireframes)
- Variety of contexts and stakeholder needs require flexible design approaches
- Time constraints and availability of stakeholders are key challenges
- Combination of digital tools (video conferencing, shared docs, virtual whiteboards) effective for collaboration
- Some stakeholders able to engage more deeply in game design process than anticipated

Conclusions:

- Pilots provided valuable lessons and built capacity for future case studies
- Need for customized activity designs based on stakeholder context and needs
- Importance of efficient time use and flexible engagement options
- Consider options for compensating non-professional participants
- Potential for deeper stakeholder involvement in game development process
- Findings will inform implementation of future case studies with authentic policy stakeholders

GAME TOOLS & PLATFORMS

Game Tools and Platforms

Overview

Two platforms: DiBL (Dilemma-based Learning) and PlanetPlay (PP) Survey Tech

- Used for policy maker reflection sessions
- Adapted through iterative agile process

DiBL	PlanetPlay
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Facilitator-driven multiplayer dilemma games• Visual game creator• Analytics dashboard• Localization support	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• In-game survey system• Distribution through mobile games• Real-time data collection and analysis

Analytics Dashboard

Combines data from both platforms
Built using Retool and Tinybird
Provides visualizations and report

GREAT D3.1 Functional Specification of game tools and platforms V3

This deliverable introduces the two platforms (DiBL & PlayMob) that are applied throughout the projec...

 Zenodo

DiBL Platform Demo

The screenshot displays the DiBL platform's 'Cases' management interface. At the top, the DiBL logo is on the left, and navigation links for 'Dashboard', 'Cases', 'Layouts', 'Facilitator Cases', 'Sessions', 'Organizations', and 'Files' are in the center. The user's name, 'Simon Egerfeldt-Nielsen', is shown on the right. Below the navigation is a 'Cases' header with a dropdown menu set to 'Demo' and an '+ Add Case' button. A table titled 'All Cases (1)' contains one row of data:

NAME	FOLDER	ORGANIZATION	CREATED BY	EDITED BY	EDITED TIME	
DIBL101	January 2025	Demo	Simon Egerfeldt-Nielsen	Simon Egerfeldt-Nielsen	12/01/2025 15:48	⋮

Below the table are icons for 'Previous', 'Current', and 'Next' case, and a large play button icon. In the bottom left corner, there is a circular profile picture of a man with a beard and short hair.

Sign up for [free here](#)

PlanetPlay Platform User Walkthrough

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Underpinning Research Framework

Overview:

- Multi-disciplinary research project on using games to engage citizens in climate change policy
- Adopts a Methodology for Interdisciplinary Research (MIR) framework
- Incorporates Citizen Science approaches throughout

Key Points:

- Uses multiple case studies across 5 project cycles
- Two main research tools:
 - Short interactions via Playmob/PlanetPlay platform
 - Long interactions via SGI's dilemma-based games
- Collaborative study design with stakeholders
- Data analysis combines quantitative and qualitative methods
- Follows case study best practices for validity and reliability

Conclusion:

- Complex project requiring flexible, multi-faceted methodology
- Aims to produce insights on game-based citizen engagement that are generalizable and cumulative across cases
- Balances rigorous academic research with practical stakeholder needs

Figure 1: The Multi Interdisciplinary Framework (MIR), adapted from Tobi and Kampen (2018).

Case Study Design Methods

Overview:

- Details the case study design process for the GREAT project
- Incorporates an 8-stage process based on Multi Interdisciplinary Research (MIR) framework
- Provides implementation guidance for all stages of the case study process

Key Points:

- Case study is the primary research instrument in the GREAT project
- Multiple-case design approach adopted to generate data through replication
- 8-step process (see cycle)
- Evaluation and reporting procedures outlined
- Tailored evaluation designs for different activities (quiz games, dilemma games, citizen science)

Conclusion:

- Scalable design can inform future case study research in digital domains
- Aims to strengthen citizen voice and improve engagement in climate change and sustainable development issues
- Designed to identify characteristics that strengthen citizens' abilities to act as agents of change

Figure 2. GREAT Case Study Cycle Partners

GREAT D4.2 GREAT Case Study Plan

This deliverable provides details of the Case Study design methods and process to be deployed in the project. The design incorporates an instantiated...

Research Cycle

DiBL CASE STUDY EXAMPLE: Rooftop Revolution

Rooftop Revolution: Using Games for Urban Sustainability

Overview:

Case study exploring the use of a serious dilemma game to engage stakeholders on green rooftop implementation in Cyprus.

Key Points:

- 97 participants across 7 game sessions
- Explored benefits, barriers, and incentives for green roofs
- Game facilitated diverse perspectives and constructive debates
- Role-playing enhanced empathy and problem-solving
- Financial support and maintenance assistance identified as key incentives
- Safety, long-term sustainability, and costs seen as main barriers

Conclusion:

Serious games show promise as an innovative tool for urban planning consultation, fostering inclusive dialogue and generating actionable insights for sustainable urban development.

Rooftop Revolution: Using Games for Urban Sustainability

 GCS4 Case Study Rooftop Revolution Cyprus
This report is an overview of the case study 'Rooftop Revolution' (GCS4). 'Rooftop Revolution' is the...
 Zenodo

PLANETPLAY CASE STUDY

EXAMPLE: UNDP

Play2Act / Data Insights

PlanetPlay & GREAT* partnered with **UNDP** for the Play2Act survey, reaching out to global citizens through **direct in-game links**. The project will last for **minimum 2 years** with bi-annual polling and will be the largest climate survey in history. During the 1st roll out (2024), we reached **229 countries** and engaged with **over 1 million players**. The data has been reported to UNDP for analysis and as well been reported back to game studios on insights, for example, insights relating to player sentiment per demographics.

1+
million
gamers engaging

229
Countries
responded
(189 per UN definition)

Play2Act

The largest in-game poll to explore climate and environmental action backed by the UN.

[Learn More →](#)

Peoples' Climate Vote

RESULTS

*GREAT (Games Realising Effective and Affective Transition) is a 3 year EU Commission funded project including a number of academic institutions and PlanetPlay on researches about games and its power of influence. Play2Act survey is one of the research cases in GREAT project.

Dissemination Roundtables

To kick off the Play2Act case study, a roundtable was held in New York at the UNDP office bringing together games studios and UNDP climate and policy experts, to discuss the role of gaming as part of the Climate promise.

Playmob/PlanetPlay Lead Delegation of Games Studios at UNDP Climate Promise Event - The GREAT Project

During Earth Week 2024, CEOs Jude Ower and Rhea Loucas discussed how the games industry can support climate action by leveraging games to mobilize players for climate advocacy.

greatproject.gg/

Dissemination & Exploitation Roundtables

Before the Play2Act case study went live there was a meeting hosted by SYBO games as one of the lead partners on Play2Act, during Climate Week in NYC in September 2024. This was an opportunity to bring together games studios, climate experts and policy makers, to discuss the role of gaming in policy making and the GREAT methodology, to inspire stakeholders to adopt the vision.

Case Study Report Play2Act
The Play2Act case study builds upon the GCS1 Exploratory study by validating the integration of digital surveys into gaming environments as a tool...
 Zenodo

Gaming for Good: Harnessing the power of gaming to advance the sustainabilit...
The gaming industry, with over 3 billion players globally and annual revenues surpassing \$200...
 Zenodo

Case Study Outcome PR

Almost 50% of players make greener choices playing games addressing climate change
Almost 50% of gamers have reduced their environmental impact after playing games highlighting the issues of climate cha...
GamesIndustry.biz / May 13

Gaming for the planet: Can video games help drive climate action?
Global initiative led by non-profit PlanetPlay and UN Development Programme points to huge potential for video games to drive awareness and action on the climate and nature crises
businessinsider.com / May 13

Games with green messages can change your behaviour in real life, new study finds
These are some impressive numbers.
Radio Times / Jan 2, 2024

PlanetPlay's Play2Act poll finds 79% make positive change after playing green games
PlanetPlay announced that data from an in-game poll called Play2Act showed gaming can incentivize greener habits among gamers.
GamesBeat / May 12

Video Game Survey Finds Players Alter Behaviour in Response to Climate Themes
"With a combined reach of 80 million players per week, Play2Act is now the largest study of its kind—gathering insights on how players feel about the environment, and how green games influence real-world behaviour,...
The Energy Mix / May 15

CASE STUDIES:

In more detail

More Detail: Case Study Toolkits

[Toolkit: Prosper](#) - The GREAT Project

Prosper: a cooperative policy-making simulation game about the UN's Sustainable Development Goals. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game.

Toolkit: Prosper - The GREAT Project

Prosper: a cooperative policy-making simulation game about the UN's Sustainable Development Goals. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game.

greatproject.gg/

[Toolkit: Green Rooftops](#) - The GREAT Project

Green Rooftops: Playful policy-making and reflective roleplaying exercises about green utilization of rooftop spaces. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game.

Toolkit: Green Rooftops - The GREAT Project

Green Rooftops: Playful policy-making and reflective roleplaying exercises about green utilization of rooftop spaces. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game.

greatproject.gg/

[Toolkit: Green Jobs](#) - The GREAT Project

Green Jobs: A roleplaying exercise about getting young people interested in the developing sector of green jobs. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game.

Toolkit: Green Jobs - The GREAT Project

Green Jobs: A roleplaying exercise about getting young people interested in the developing sector of green jobs. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game.

greatproject.gg/

[Toolkit: Waterwise](#) - The GREAT Project

Waterwise: a facilitated learning game about water scarcity. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game.

Toolkit: Waterwise - The GREAT Project

Waterwise: a facilitated learning game about water scarcity. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game.

greatproject.gg/

EVALUATION

Evaluation Framework

Overview:

- GREAT used game-based methods to engage citizens on climate crisis
- Evaluation framework combines public engagement, gamification, and climate change concepts
- Focus on 4 impact dimensions: scientific, individual actors, economic, societal

Figure 3: The theoretical framework forming the basis for the GREAT project evaluation

Evaluation Framework

Key Findings:

- Logic models developed for each dimension to show relationships between inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes and impacts
- Mixed methods approach with qualitative and quantitative data collection
- Indicators defined for each dimension, linked to theoretical concepts
- Two game interventions evaluated: DIBL and PlanetPlay

Conclusion:

- Comprehensive, modular evaluation approach
- Will be tailored to specific case studies
- Aims to assess short-term outcomes and potential long-term impacts
- Provides evidence on effectiveness of game-based participatory processes for climate engagement

**CHANGE
THE WORLD**

ONE GAME AT A

TIME